

THE EFFICACY OF DICTOGLOSS AS A PEDAGOGICAL TOOL IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Ganiyeva Dilfuzaxon Qodirjon qizi

Guliston davlat universiteti

Ingliz tili va adabiyoti kafedراسi o'qituvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11178094>

ANNOTATION

Dictogloss, a form of dictation-based language teaching, involves students listening to a text, reconstructing it from memory, and comparing their version with the original. In this article, identifying optimal conditions for implementing dictogloss activities and explore potential variations in its application across different proficiency levels and language learning settings are seen. The findings of this study are expected to contribute valuable insights to language teaching methodologies and inform educators about the efficacy of dictogloss as a pedagogical tool.

Keywords: Dictogloss, language learning, pedagogy, effectiveness, methodology

Language educators continually seek innovative approaches to facilitate language learning and enhance learners' proficiency. Dictogloss, a pedagogical technique rooted in dictation exercises, has emerged as a promising tool in language teaching. This article provides a comprehensive review of research on dictogloss, aiming to elucidate its effectiveness in language learning contexts. By examining empirical studies and theoretical frameworks, this review seeks to inform educators about the potential benefits and optimal practices associated with dictogloss activities.

Dictogloss is grounded in constructivist and sociocultural theories of language learning, which emphasize the importance of interaction, negotiation of meaning, and cognitive engagement in the learning process. According to these theories, dictogloss promotes active engagement with language through listening, processing, and reconstructing textual input, thereby facilitating language acquisition. Additionally, dictogloss aligns with principles of task-based language teaching, promoting authentic communication and meaningful language use in classroom settings.

Dictogloss (dictation + glossary) as an interactive method was first introduced by Vajrib in Ruth Waynerub's (1990) book Grammar dictation. Dictogloss is one of the types of dictation, the purpose of which, in essence, is similar to traditional dictation and is to repeat and restore the text heard by students by bringing its content and lexical-grammatical content as close as

possible to the original. In dictogloss, a short text is read aloud to students at a medium speed, and they record key words as they listen. After the dictation is read, they compose a text using the words they have recorded. In small groups, the group members together rewrite the original text using the key words that each of them recorded, and at the end of this process, they compare and analyze the original text. The emphasis is mainly on grammar. According to Ruth, dictogloss is performed in five stages.

a) a small text is read twice to students at medium speed.

b) in the process of reading, students write down important words and phrases.

d) working in small groups, students create a text using the words and phrases they re-recorded.

e) students of each group develop their own revised version, paying attention to grammatical structure and content accuracy, but the original text is not repeated.

f) various copies are analyzed and checked, and students delete unnecessary parts of the text they have created, correct and discuss it.[2,5-6]

Dictogloss is fundamentally different from traditional dictation and its types, not only for understanding grammar rules and applying them, but also for student interactivity. written work used to teach the rules of punctuation and to test proficiency in those rules. Dictogloss is similar to dictation in that it reflects the process of dictation being read aloud.

In order to master grammar rules, it is important for learners to practice them so that they can use them later in communication. It is the interactive method of dictogloss that helps students to strengthen the learned grammatical rules and new words. In addition, dictogloss develops language skills such as reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills, as well as English literacy skills, i.e., acquisition of spelling rules like traditional dictation.

When using Dictogloss, students work together and it helps them share ideas by discussing and sharing information that is interesting and learned. During the exchange of ideas, they communicate with each other, and they also apply the learned language material in practice. Since new words on the topic are repeated at each stage of the process, students can easily learn and memorize them during the lesson. In addition to the advantages mentioned above, Dictogloss is also a motivational method for learning a foreign language.

Dictogloss is also effective in preventing and correcting grammatical errors in students' written speech. It also facilitates the introduction of scientific

language and complex grammatical rules and their use in written speech. For example, in the formation of students' essay writing skills, it is useful to introduce the essay model that creates difficulties for them. Its best feature is the ease of preparation and organization of this process for the teacher. Important recommendations for teachers for using Dictogloss:

-before students begin this process, choose a text and source that have one paragraph

- your chosen text should be a good example for using language material and form;

- try to use visual aids while reading the text

-repeat key words for new learners and help.

The use of Dictogloss reveals its linguo-didactic character, assimilation of language material and grammatical rules in mutual cooperation between the teacher and students, and the ability to apply them in oral and written communication. The effectiveness of its use in English language classes has been tested in several studies and positive results have been achieved.

References:

1.Аксенова И.Н Методика обучения студентов видам иноязычной коммуникативной деятельности на основе диктоглосса (английский язык, языковой факультет) ААД, - М.,2023

2. Wajnryb. R. Grammar dictation.- Oxford:Oxford University Press,1990

3.O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi. Birinchi jild. Toshkent, 2020

4. McLeod.A.K. Beyond grammar teaching:Dictogloss strategies for improving literacy.English teaching Forum. americanenglish.state.gov/forum

5. Sayed. M. Using dictogloss strategy for developing secondary stage students' English Grammar competence and Motivation towards learning English language// BSU Journal of pedagogy and Curriculum, 2023; 2(3): 134-152